

Research Article

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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF AN ENHANCED IRON SUPPLEMENT BLENDS OF MILLET, SOYBEANS AND BAOBAB LEAF FOR IRON-DEFICIENCY ANAEMIA MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Essential mineral deficiencies are still prevalent in developing countries where many people consume monotonous predominantly cereal-based food. This study aimed to evaluate the potential of including tropical plants high in iron (baobab leaf) in pearl millet-based food with soybean and the management of iron deficiency anaemia. The samples: millet (M), soybean (SB), and baobab leaf (BL) were grouped as Formula 1 (40% M: 40% SB: 20% BL), Formula 2 (20% M: 60% SB: 30% BL) Formula 3 (10% M: 30% SB: 60% BL), Formula 4 (20% M: 20% SB: 60% BL) and Formula 5 (40% M: 30% SB: 30% BL) while ferrous sulphate was used as a standard. The samples were assayed for vitamin and mineral element composition using standard methods. The results obtained were subjected to statistical analysis. An increase and decrease pattern were observed in the mineral contents of the samples after processing. Among the formulas, Na was higher in Formula 1, Ca in Formula 2, while Fe was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher in Formula 3 and 4. The iron content of Formulas 3 and 4 was higher than the RDA for adults, but very close to that of children, and lower than that of the control. A significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed in the vitamin content of all the samples. Furthermore, formulas with higher percentages of millet and baobab leaves tend to have higher levels of vitamins A, B₁, B₁₂, and B₃. This study has demonstrated the feasibility of creating a nutritious formula using baobab leaves, notably the inclusion of baobab leaves has significantly enhanced the iron content of the formula, offering a promising alternative for the management of iron deficiency anaemia.

Keywords: Iron-rich formula; Nutritional Anaemia; Ferrous Sulphate; Proximate Composition

INTRODUCTION

The most salient nutritional disorder developing countries are facing is childhood anaemia, which is one of the major public health issues around the world, it is especially predominant in developing continents such as Asia and Africa and Nigeria are no exception. The WHO has declared that Africa and Southeast Asia have the most elevated risk, where around 66% of preschool children are suffering from anaemia [1]. Anaemia is defined as the reduction in red blood cell count, haemoglobin or haematocrit. The normal range of haemoglobin levels in men is 13.5 to 18.0 g/dL, women 12.0 to 15.0 g/dL and children 11.0 to 16.0 g/dL. Nearly 400 types of anaemia were divided into three groups based on their cause. The major causes of anaemia are blood loss, decreased or faulty red blood cell synthesis, and the destruction of red blood cells. In children, the major health consequences of anaemia include impaired cognitive and physical development, increased mortality and morbidity, and low intake of the iron-rich formula is the main cause at anaemia, other causes include infections, diseases and deficiency of micronutrients such as folate and Vitamin B₁₂. Iron-deficiency anaemia is the most prevalent anaemia worldwide.[1]

It is a major global health problem that impacts child mortality, maternity problems and physical health. This occurs due to the lack of iron, which is important for the production of haemoglobin in the red blood cells. Poor dietary intake of iron leads to Iron deficiency anaemia [2]. Iron-deficiency anaemia is by far the first cause of nutritional anaemia worldwide, it is worth noting that anaemia, especially Iron-deficiency anaemia, can be prevented or managed using Iron-rich food formula.

Millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) is a group of cereals that belongs to the *Poaceae* family, which is widely consumed and contains major and minor nutrients in remarkable amounts [3]. Millets provide more essential amino acids than most other cereals, these compounds are the building blocks of protein. Large millets include: pearl, foxtail, proso, finger (or ragi). Small millets include: Kodo, Barnyard, Little Guinea, Browntop, Fonio, Adlay (or Job's tears). Pearl millet is the most widely produced variety intended for human consumption. Still, all types are renowned for their high nutritional value and health benefits.

Soybean (*Glycine max*) is a leguminous vegetable of the pea family that grows in tropical, subtropical, and temperate climates. It consists of more than 36% protein, 30% carbohydrates, and excellent amounts of dietary fibre, vitamins, and minerals. It also consists of 20% oil, which makes it the most important crop for producing edible oil [4]. It contains about 3.9 – 5.36% minerals determined as ash [5]. The major mineral constituents are potassium, calcium, magnesium and phosphorus. However, a substantial amount of the phosphorous in soybean is found in bound form and hence is not available for human use [6] estimated total phosphorus in soybean as 20.82 mg/g while available phosphorus was 11.97 mg/g. In addition, the biological utilization of most minerals such as zinc (Zn), iron (Fe), magnesium (Mg) and calcium (Ca) is impaired by phytic acid [6].

Baobab (*Adansonia digitata*) is a deciduous tree that is native to Africa, Australia, and the Middle East. The bark, seed, and fruits are medicinal, and baobab leaves are highly nutritious and have been traditionally used to treat many kinds of diseases such as malaria, tuberculosis, anaemia, dysentery, and toothache [7]. The iron-rich supplements are not available, especially in rural areas and are highly expensive and out of the reach of poor people even in urban areas. The locally available raw materials within an area such as cereal, legumes, and vegetables are very rich in iron content especially when they are formulated into a single formula. This can be used to manage anaemia, in children and even among elders who become vulnerable to the disease as a result of a lack of awareness of the iron-rich sources which are locally available, affordable, and accessible.

Iron deficiency anaemia poses a significant public health threat ranging from fatigue, weakness, pale/yellowish skin, abnormal heartbeats, and short breath, affecting millions of people worldwide, particularly in developing countries, Nigeria is no exception especially here in the Northeastern part of Nigeria that has been ravaged by insurgency. Globally it is estimated to have affected 40% of children aged 6-59 months, 37% of pregnant women and 30% of women 15-49 years of age. The persistence of iron deficiency anaemia in these regions can be attributed to inadequate nutrition and the high cost of essential medications. In response to this challenge, it is imperative to explore alternative dietary sources rich in iron to combat iron deficiency anaemia [7]. Therefore, by harnessing the nutritional benefits of Millet, Soybeans, and Baobab leaf, an innovative, iron-rich dietary solution can be developed to alleviate the burden of iron deficiency anaemia. This initiative has the potential to improve the health and well-being of millions of people worldwide, particularly in resource-constrained settings. Therefore, this work aimed at producing iron-rich formulas for the management of nutritional anaemia, particularly iron-deficiency anaemia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

The millet, soybean, and baobab leaf (dried) were obtained from Gaboru Market in Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. The samples were identified by a Botanist at the Department of Biological Science, University of Maiduguri.

Sample Preparation

The samples were sorted to get rid of foreign matter, and stored in an air-tight container at ambient temperature (36°C) until analysis.

Millet

Ten kilograms (10 kg) of cleaned millet sample was soaked in two litres (2L) of distilled water for 72 hr. for the fermentation process to take place. The fermented grains were then transferred to a grease-free tray and sun-dried for two days. The grains were milled, and a sieve of 5 mm pores was used to remove the larger bits. The obtained material and stored in an airtight container until use [8].

Soybean

About 300g of dirt-free soybeans were roasted, milled, and stored in an air-tight transparent plastic container at room temperature until required [9].

Baobab Leaf

The leaves were soaked, washed, sun-dried, de-stalked, and pulverized. The powder obtained was sieved into a fine powder using a 3mm sieve [10].

Scheme 1: Preparation of Iron-rich Formula from Millet, Soybean, and Baobab Leaf Source: [11]

Determination of Mineral Content

Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) AA 6800 series Shimadzu Corp was used for the determination of calcium, Sodium, Potassium, Iron, Manganese, Magnesium, and Zinc (Ca, Na, K, Fe, Mn, Mg, and Zn).

Two grams of sample was weighed into a crucible and incinerated at 600°C in a carbolite muffle furnace for three (3) hours. To the ashed sample, exactly 10.0 mL 6 N HCl was added and placed on a water bath and boiled for 10 minutes. The samples were removed and filtered into a 100 mL volumetric flask. The filter paper was held down and the volume was made up to 100 mL using deionized water. Ten millilitres of the digested sample were transferred to the sample container and aspirated to the AAS; the reading was recorded in ppm [12].

The appropriate lamps and correct wavelength for each element are specified in the instruction manual as follows: Fe=248.3 nm, K=766.5 nm, Zn=213.9 nm, Mn=279.5 nm, Na=589.0 nm, Ca=422.7 nm, Mg=285.23 nm

Extraction of Vitamin for Analysis

Exactly 0.2 g of the samples was placed into 100 mL volumetric flasks; 80 mL of water was added to each flask. After 15 min. of ultrasonic mixing, the samples were spun at 5000 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant was filtered through a 0.45 µm nylon membrane filter [13].

Determination of Vitamin Content

A Merck-Hitachi liquid chromatography system (Merck Darmstadt, Germany) equipped with a Model L-600 pump, a Model AS-200 automatic injector and a Model L-4000 variable wavelength UV/Vis detector was used. The chromatographic column is a reversed-phase chromatographic column, particle size 5µ (Merck). The mobile phase was 0.1 % TFA (Trifluoroacetic acid) and 100 % ACN (Acetonitrile) with a flow rate of 1.8 ml/min. The

mobile phase was filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane and degassed using an Ultrasonic machine before use. The UV/VIS detector was set at 260 nm [3][12].

Data Analysis

All analyses were carried out in triplicates, and the results were expressed as mean \pm SEM. The SPSS 23.0 for Windows Computer Software Package was used for the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), followed by Duncan's multiple ranges to compare means. P values less than 0.05 is considered significant ($P < 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Table 1 presents the mineral element composition of raw and processed samples of soybeans, millet, and baobab leaf. The results show a significant decrease in the sodium concentration of the samples after processing, while Ca and Mg show a significant increase in soybeans after processing, but for millet a significant reduction was observed, for K a significant reduction was observed after processing of soybean, while millet shows no significant difference. However, for processed baobab leaf a significant increase was observed after processing. The iron content of soybean and millet is significant ($P < 0.05$), while for baobab leaf a significant ($P < 0.05$) disease was observed. The processed samples of soybeans and baobab leaf show a significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in Zn content, while millet did not show any significant ($P < 0.050$) difference after processing.

The mineral element composition of the formula is presented in Table 2. The result of the content of the formula ranges between (24.10-64.00) Mg/100g, with formula 1 having the highest sodium content followed by formula 4, while formula 2 had the lowest sodium content of (24.10mg/kg. The sodium content of formulas 4 and 5 show no significant ($P < 0.05$) difference. The calcium content of formulas 1,2,3,4, and 5 were 4.10mg/100g, 6.13mg/100g, 7.20mg/100g, and 6.10mg/100g respectively. Among the formulas. Formula 4 had the highest calcium content. The calcium content of formulas 1 and 3 shows no significant ($P < 0.05$) difference, a similar pattern was observed in the calcium content of formulas 2 and 5. The increasing pattern of the magnesium content was observed from formula 1, across to 2 down to formula 5, with formula 5 having the highest magnesium content of 4.10mg/100g while formula 1 recorded the lowest magnesium content of 1.06mg/100g. The differences were significant ($P < 0.05$). No significant difference was observed in the potassium content of all the samples. The iron content of the formulated samples was 1056mg/100g, 6.29mg/100g, 14.87mg/100g, 13.20mg/100g and 18.82mg/100g for formulas 1,2,3,4 and 5 respectively, with formulas 3 and 4 recording the highest iron content of 14.87mg/100g and 13.20mg/100g respectively.

Table 1: Mineral Composition of Unprocessed and Processed Soybean, Millet and Baobab Leaf (mg/100g)

Nutrients	Components						Control
	Millet		Soybean		Baobab leaf		
	Raw	Processed	Raw	Processed	Raw	Processed	
Na	69.80 ^c \pm 0.06	51.00 ^c \pm 0.06	29.22 ^b \pm 0.06	18.40 ^a \pm 0.06	56.20 ^d \pm 0.06	16.40 ^a \pm 0.06	ND
Ca	6.10 ^a \pm 0.06	2.84 ^b \pm 0.01	6.10 ^a \pm 0.06	8.30 ^d \pm 0.06	2.80 ^b \pm 0.06	4.20 ^c \pm 0.06	ND
Mg	2.81 ^b \pm 0.0	1.83 ^b \pm 0.06	3.10 ^b \pm 0.06	4.10 ^c \pm 0.01	9.10 ^d \pm 0.06	1.69 ^a \pm 0.07	ND
K	0.27 ^a \pm 0.0	0.21 ^a \pm 0.01	0.32 ^b \pm 0.01	0.22 ^a \pm 0.01	0.17 ^a \pm 0.01	0.31 ^b \pm 0.01	ND
Fe	5.28 ^c \pm 0.01	9.02 ^b \pm 0.01	8.86 ^b \pm 0.01	13.2 ^a \pm 0.01	13.62 ^a \pm 0.01	10.12 ^b \pm 0.01	50mg
Zn	0.48 ^b \pm 0.01	0.44 ^b \pm 0.01	0.54 ^d \pm 0.01	0.30 ^a \pm 0.01	0.34 ^a \pm 0.01	0.17 ^c \pm 0.01	ND
Mn	0.10 ^a \pm 0.01	0.18 ^a \pm 0.01	0.14 ^a \pm 0.01	0.27 ^b \pm 0.01	0.07 ^a \pm 0.01	0.14 ^a \pm 0.01	ND

Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM, of three determinations. Values with different superscripts horizontally along the row are significantly different. ($P < 0.05$); n=3, Key:ND = Not Determined

Table 2: Mineral Composition of the Produced Formula (mg/100g)

Nutrients	Formulas						RDA of children (3-5 years)	RDA of Adult	RDA of pregnant women
	Formula 1	Formula 2	Formula 3	Formula 4	Formula 5	Control			
Na	64.00 ^d ±0.58	24.10 ^b ±0.06	17.00 ^a ±0.06	41.80 ^c ±0.06	43.80 ^c ±0.06	ND	1200	2300	3000
Ca	4.10 ^b ±0.06	6.13 ^a ±0.06	4.30 ^b ±0.06	7.20 ^c ±0.06	6.10 ^a ±0.06	ND	120	700	750
Mg	1.07 ^b ±0.06	3.10 ^a ±0.06	2.20 ^b ±0.06	3.12 ^a ±0.01	4.10 ^c ±0.06	ND	6000	370	350
K	0.21 ^b ±0.01	0.18 ^a ±0.01	0.25 ^b ±0.01	0.22 ^c ±0.01	0.18 ^a ±0.01	ND	2500	340	360
Fe	10.56 ^d ±0.01	6.29 ^b ±0.01	14.87 ^a ±0.01	13.20 ^a ±0.01	8.82 ^c ±0.01	50mg	15	8	30
Zn	0.47 ^a ±0.01	0.28 ^b ±0.01	0.31 ^b ±0.01	0.44 ^a ±0.01	0.18 ^b ±0.01	ND	80	9	1
Mn	0.18 ^b ±0.01	0.12 ^a ±0.01	0.21 ^b ±0.01	0.07 ^c ±0.01	0.11 ^a ±0.01	ND	0.3	2	2

Data are expressed as mean ± SEM, of three determinations. Values with different superscripts horizontally along the row are significantly different. (P < 0.05).

Key: Formula 1 = 40% Millet: 40% Soybean: 20% Baobab leaf; Formula 2 = 20% Millet: 60% Soybean: 30% Baobab leaf

Formula 3 = 10% Millet: 30% Soybean: 60% Baobab leaf; Formula 4 = 20% Millet: 20% Soybean: 60% Baobab leaf

Formula 5 = 40% Millet: 30% Soybean: 30% Baobab leaf; ND = Not Determined. RDA = Recommended Dietary Allowance

Vitamin Content of Raw and Processed Samples

The result of the vitamin content of millet in Table 3 shows a significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in vitamin A₁, B₁, B₁₂, and B₃ after processing, except for vitamin C where no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference was observed after processing for soybeans. No significant difference was observed in with A, B₁ and C while vitamin B₁₂ and B₃ showed a significant ($P < 0.05$) difference, vitamin A, B₃, and B₁₂ of Baobab leaf did not show a significant ($P > 0.05$) reduction after processing the vitamin content of all the sample analysis were above the RDA for children, adult and pregnant women except for vitamin C and B₃ were their content is below the RDA for children, adult and pregnant women.

The results of the Vitamin composition of Formulated Formula are shown in Table 4 No significant ($P > 0.05$) difference was observed in the vitamin content of formula 1 and 2 while, compared to formula 3, 4 and 5 a significant ($P < 0.05$) higher, vitamin A content was observed in formula 3, 4 and compared to 1 and 2 vitamin A content of the formulated were higher than the vitamin A daily requirement for children adult and pregnant women, the vitamin B₁ content of formula 1 is 3.88mg/100g while for formula 2,3,4 and I were 2.69mg/100g, 1.2mg/100g, 0.44mg/100g and 1.80mg/100g respectively, the difference ($P < 0.05$) were significantly higher and the values of Vit B₁ were higher than the RDA values to children, adult and pregnant women vitamin B₁₂ and C of the sample shows significant ($P < 0.05$) difference except for B₁₂, while vitamin C content of the formulated formula was below the RDA of children, adult, pregnant women. Vitamin B₃ of the formulated formula ranges between 0.13 to 3.38. Formula 1 recorded the highest B₃ content of 3.38mg/100g, while Formula 2 recorded the lowest content of vitamin B₃.

Table 3: Vitamins Composition of Unprocessed and Processed Soybean, Millet and Baobab Leaf ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$)

Vitamins	Components					
	Millet		Soybean		Baobab Leaf	
	Raw	Processed	Raw	Processed	Raw	Processed
Vit. A	2.71 ^d ±0.001	1.85 ^c ±0.001	2.10 ^a ±0.001	2.11 ^a ±0.001	1.27 ^b ±0.001	1.22 ^b ±0.001
Vit. B ₁	1.51 ^b ±0.001	0.46 ^a ±0.001	1.78 ^b ±0.001	1.57 ^b ±0.001	1.81 ^b ±0.001	0.59 ^a ±0.001
Vit. B ₁₂	0.61 ^b ±0.001	0.34 ^a ±0.001	0.46 ^a ±0.001	0.75 ^b ±0.001	0.23 ^a ±0.001	0.37 ^a ±0.001
Vit. C	0.35 ^a ±0.001	0.25 ^a ±0.001	0.30 ^a ±0.001	0.45 ^a ±0.001	0.62 ^b ±0.46	0.23 ^a ±0.01
Vit B ₃	0.59 ^b ±0.001	0.40 ^a ±0.001	0.48 ^a ±0.001	0.73 ^b ±0.001	0.25 ^a ±0.001	0.37 ^a ±0.001

Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM, of three determinations. Values with different superscripts along the row are significantly different. ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4: Vitamins Composition of Produced Formula ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$)

Vitamins	Formulas						RDA (children 3-5 years)	RDA of(Adult)	RDA (Pregnant women)
	Formula 1	Formula 2	Formula 3	Formula 4	Formula 5				
Vit. A	0.94 ^a ±0.001	0.71 ^a ±0.0003	2.24 ^b ±0.0003	1.80 ^c ±0.001	2.26 ^b ±0.001	0.4	0.9	0.1	
Vit. B ₁	3.86 ^d ±0.001	2.69 ^c ±0.0003	1.24 ^b ±0.001	0.44 ^a ±0.001	1.80 ^b ±0.001	0.6	1.2	1.4	
Vit. B ₁₂	2.82 ^c ±0.001	0.13 ^a ±0.001	0.79 ^b ±0.001	0.49 ^a ±0.001	0.74 ^b ±0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	
Vit. C	1.86 ^c ±0.001	0.08 ^b ±0.001	0.48 ^a ±0.001	0.30 ^a ±0.001	0.41 ^a ±0.001	3	80	85	
Vit B ₃	3.38 ^b ±0.001	0.13 ^a ±0.001	0.92 ^a ±0.001	0.53 ^a ±0.001	0.68 ^a ±0.001	8	16	18	

Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM, of three determinations. Values with different superscripts along the row are significantly different. ($P < 0.05$).

Key:

Formula 1 = 40% Millet: 40% Soybean: 20% Baobab leaf; Formula 2 = 20% Millet: 60% Soybean: 30% Baobab leaf

Formula 3 = 10% Millet: 30% Soybean: 60% Baobab leaf; Formula 4 = 20% Millet: 20% Soybean: 60% Baobab leaf
Formula 5 = 40% Millet: 30% Soybean: 30% Baobab leaf; RDA = Recommended Dietary Allowance

Discussion

Minerals are essential nutrients that help maintain tissue, support the development and health of bones and teeth, act as cofactors and coenzymes to various enzyme systems, help regulate and coordinate the majority of bodily functions, and support other physiological and biochemical processes [14]. In this study, the loss in the levels of sodium, potassium, and zinc in the processed samples could be attributed to the loss in the ash contents during fermentation [15]. More than 50 % of the ash in millet was leached out of the steep water and washed away. A decrease in the levels of Na, K, Mg, Ca, P, and Zn levels in processed millet samples was reported by [16] the high level of Na observed in Formula 1 could be due to a high proportion of millet in the formula. However, the mineral levels observed in this study were lower than the RDA levels for children, adults and pregnant women, except for iron, where the values recorded in formulas 3 and 4 are closer to the RDA for children, higher than RDA for adult, but lower than that of the control and RDA for pregnant women. The increase observed in the Fe content of Formula 3 and 4 probably may be due to the inclusion of a high proportion of Baobab leaf which was reported to have higher iron contents of more than 10 times higher than soybean.

Iron has been reported to be an important component of the red blood cells, while its deficiency is believed to affect 35-50% of the world's population, making it the most common micronutrient deficiency in the world. Formulas with higher baobab leaf content generally have higher potassium and magnesium levels, e.g., unprocessed baobab leaves. Processing generally reduces mineral content, as seen in processed millet and processed baobab leaves for various minerals like calcium, magnesium, and zinc. Processing of soybean (e.g., Processed Soybean) enhances iron and zinc content significantly compared to other forms. The data underscore the importance of formula composition and processing methods in determining the mineral content of foods. Higher baobab leaf and soybean content generally contributes to higher mineral concentrations, while processing tends to reduce mineral levels. These insights are crucial for dietary planning and nutritional enrichment strategies in food formulation.

The reduction in vitamin levels observed in the fermented millet may be attributed to the fermentation process. During fermentation, a significant portion of the vitamins likely leached into the water, which was later discarded along with the liquid [5].

Vitamins are essential nutrients needed by the body in small amounts for various metabolic functions. Consuming foods rich in vitamins helps prevent deficiencies that can lead to various health problems, such as scurvy (lack of Vitamin C), or night blindness (lack of Vitamin A). Vitamins can affect the sensory qualities of food, such as colour, flavour, and texture [5]. The values of the vitamin C obtained from this study were significantly lower when compared with the values (0.61 to 33.13 mg/100 g) reported by [5]. The loss of vitamin C during heat treatments has been attributed to a combination of leaching and chemical destruction [17]. The vitamin B₃ (Nicotinamide) content of the samples ranged from 0.13 to 3.38 µg/100 g.

Formula 1 (3.38 µg/100g), Unprocessed Millet (0.59 µg/100g), and Unprocessed Soybean (0.48 µg/100g) while the lowest value of vitamin B₃ was recorded in Formula 2 (0.13 µg/100g) among all the samples. The presence of vitamins in all the samples is a pointer to the beneficial nutritional values of soybean, millet, and baobab leaf. Formulas with higher percentages of millet and baobab leaves tend to have higher levels of Vitamins A, B₁, B₁₂, and B₃. Processed forms generally exhibit lower vitamin contents compared to their unprocessed counterparts, especially noticeable in millet and soybean. Vitamin C content varies widely across samples, with higher amounts found in formula 1 and some unprocessed sources. Ensuring adequate levels of vitamins in food products is often required by food safety regulations to maintain nutritional claims and standards.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Iron content varied significantly, with processed soybeans showing the highest iron levels. Baobab leaves contribute to higher potassium, magnesium, and calcium levels. However, processing generally reduced the mineral content, particularly in millet and baobab leaves. Vitamin A, B₁, and B₁₂ were higher in unprocessed ingredients, highlighting the nutritional benefits of consuming these foods in their natural form. Therefore, this study has successfully demonstrated the feasibility of creating a nutritious formula using baobab leaves notably the inclusion of baobab leaves has significantly enhanced the iron content of the formula, offering a promising alternative for the

management of iron deficiency anaemia. From the above research, it is recommended that the produced formula undergo further refortification. It is also recommended that further *in vivo* studies should be carried out.

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